
THE BENEFITS OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING IN MIXED LEVEL CLASSROOMS

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance of cooperative learning in mixed level classrooms. In order to deeply investigate the issue, the results of currently organized interview in terms of the benefits of cooperative learning in mixed level classrooms are mentioned.

Key words: cooperative learning, mixed ability classroom, peer teaching, grouping, positive interdependence.

INTRODUCTION

Cooperative learning is an instructional strategy that enables small groups of students to work together on a common assignment. The premise is simple: each person depends on and is accountable to each other. These groups work face-to-face and learn to work as a team. This approach is particularly beneficial in mixed level classrooms, where students of varying skill levels can learn together.

Cooperative learning involves more than students working together on a project. It requires teachers to structure cooperative interdependence among the students. These structures involve five key elements which are: Positive Interdependence, Individual Accountability, Promotive Interaction, Appropriate Use of Social Skills, and Group Processing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cooperative learning, also referred to as collaborative learning, encompasses a set of principles and methods aimed at optimizing the advantages derived from student collaboration. There are many definitions for cooperative learning which are not that different from each other. According to Olesen and Kagan [5.1-30], cooperative learning is a classroom activity in which the exchange of information is socially structured between learners and in which every learner is responsible for his/her understanding for the materials as well as the others' understanding for the materials at the same time. Vermette [7.101] defined cooperative learning as a team activity which include students with heterogeneous levels working together to master a body of knowledge. The spirit of the team is positive interdependence as each student is responsible for his/her own understanding and the other students' understanding. According to Johnson and Johnson [2.285], cooperative learning is an

instructional method which has some characteristics such as the responsibility of each learner for his understanding as well as the understanding of the whole team. Also, reward should be a part of cooperative learning process so that each learner should maximize his efforts to understand and motivates the other team members to increase their understanding for the success of the team. Moreover, Smith [6.153] stated that learning can be cooperative when the students work together to accomplish specific tasks. The view of Johnson and Johnson [3.358] also focused on the social skills which is one of the principles of cooperative learning. They stated that it is important for the students to believe that every individual is important for the group in order to make the cooperative learning groups cooperative in nature. They added that the students in each group should use the appropriate social skills needed for cooperative learning. This point of view is supported by Johnson who argued that in cooperative learning the students are divided into groups of four or five students in order to achieve academic content and social skills.

In cooperative learning each group is responsible for its own learning as well as the learning of all the members of the group in the sense that students can share knowledge with each other and every student can explain what s/he has gained to the other students. Thus, students in each group make discussions with each other in order to complete a task, solve a problem or achieve a specific goal given to them by the instructor. Cooperative learning does not cancel the role of the teacher because the teacher should be available in order to design the activities, monitor the students and divide them into small groups. Leaving the students alone without guidance might not help them to achieve the desired goals of learning according to Kagan [4.12-15].

One of the important advantages of cooperative learning is related to the psychological aspects of learning because using cooperative learning techniques inside the classroom helps the students to lower the level of anxiety. There is a difference between asking the student to answer a question from the side of the teacher without any practice and asking the students a question and let them discuss the answer with the other students. When the students work in groups, they will not be confused or anxious as they are going to discuss the answer with the other students to whom they feel attached and there are no barriers can be taken into consideration. The practice between the students will polish the students' skills and make them more self-confident and willing to participate in answering the questions of the teachers which reduces the communication apprehension, claimed Crandall [1.226].

METHODOLOGY

For those explanations above, the prior study explained that cooperative learning is extremely relevant to mixed ability classrooms in teaching EFL in order to create an effective learning atmosphere and make student interact with each other. Because

it is impossible to acquire a language without interaction. The aim of this research is to investigate how EFL teachers use cooperative learning strategies in their mixed ability classrooms.

N	Teachers’ pseudonyms	Grades they teach	Teachers’ degrees	Work experience
1	S.M	2 nd , 11 th	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	2 years
2	A.O’	2 nd , 11 th	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	2 years
3	X.M	7 th	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	2 years
4	M.A	6 th	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	1 year
5	M.E	1 st , 7 th , 11 th	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	1 year
6	D.I	5 th , 6 th	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	2 years
7	Z.A	1 st , 2 nd	C1 (IELTS) (Advanced)	1 year

Research method: interview. One technique in qualitative research for gathering primary data is the interview. It entails finding out what one or more people think about a business, a product, or a subject. Researchers can get comprehensive data with this strategy that may not be possible with other research techniques. While quantitative research employs numerical data and statistical analysis to explain and measure phenomena, qualitative research uses observation and interviews to explore and comprehend people's experiences and perspectives. Many study domains, such as the social sciences, psychology, health sciences, business, and education, can benefit from the use of interviews. Research findings, theoretical development, and policy suggestions can be informed by patterns, themes, and trends found in the transcription, coding, and analysis of interview data.

When: 2nd and 3th of May, 2024

Where: at public schools where the teachers of English language above work

How: face to face

Data collecting tool: interview

Interview questions:

1. How often do you give group projects to your students?

2. What factors do you consider while grouping your students?
3. How long period of time can your students work in certain groups?
4. What have you observed while your students are working in groups?

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the interview organized among young EFL public school teachers is below:

Teachers said that they use small group projects on a regular basis, such as once a week, and more peer work – in every lesson, as interaction is really important in foreign language acquisition. When it comes to factors teachers consider while grouping their students, almost all teachers claimed that they pay attention to their students’ learning abilities, social skills, learning styles, and interests. They said that they are significantly careful with gathering different ability students in a group as it help lower ability students increase engagement in lessons, with the favor of their friends. Their main goal is to create diverse groups where students can learn from each other and bring different strengths to the group. What is more, the teachers aim to encourage their shy and unsociable students to feel free and interact with their friends. Some of the interviewed teachers who educate primary school students said that they usually apply informal type of grouping which are built for one specific lesson, and the next time group members change. They consider this type of grouping is the most suitable one for young hyperactive and curious pupils as they get easily bored the same group members. The other teachers of secondary school students claimed that they usually applied formal type of grouping whose group members do not change until the end of one specific term or course. Besides, some used base groups with fixed members for the entire academic year since older students are patient enough to accomplish long-term group projects cooperatively. According to the results of the interview, the teachers often observe a variety of behaviors when students work in groups. They usually saw increased engagement in the lesson, peer correction and peer teaching, better developed social skills, and improved problem-solving abilities, especially enhanced and more fluent communication in the target language. On the one hand, they sometimes also noticed challenges such as unequal participation or difficulties with collaboration among students, which can be addressed through further instruction and support of the teacher. At times, unfortunately, some students preferred just to take advantages of other hardworking friends instead of collaborating and trying to bring benefits to their groups. However, all teachers generally gave positive comments on the practicality of cooperative learning.

CONCLUSION

Cooperative learning is a method of teaching that makes the process of language learning student-centered rather than teacher-centered. It helps the students to

socialize with each other in order to gain experience from the other students. It goes a long way with activity theory in the sense that the students become active inside the classroom. This helps the students to improve their language, get high motivation, lower the level of anxiety, and equally participate inside the classroom. The main aim of cooperative learning is to achieve a specific goal by each group inside the classroom and make every individual strong in the skill or the lesson which they study. Thus, cooperative learning has a strong foundation in research. Many hundreds of studies - by now thousands - across a wide range of subject areas and age groups have been conducted.

Cooperative learning benefits students in many ways. It is a successful teaching strategy in which small teams, each with students of different levels of ability, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject. Each member of a team is responsible for not only learning what is taught but also for helping teammates learn, thus creating an atmosphere of achievement.

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